

Yield potential

Effect of seedling age on Basmati growth and yield

M. Ashraf and S. Mahmood, Rice Program, National Agricultural Research Centre, P.O. Box 1031, Islamabad, Pakistan

Transplanting depends on a farmer's resources, particularly the availability of irrigation water, labor, and other farm inputs. However, nurseries are invariably seeded from the last week of May to the first week of Jun. Optimum

Yield and yield attributes of overage seedlings of 2 Basmati varieties. Islamabad, Pakistan.

Seedling age (d)	Basmati 370				Basmati 385			
	Productive tillers/hill (no.)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield decrease (%)	Productive tillers/hill (no.)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield decrease (%)
30	12.4	152.4	2.8	—	9.7	196.2	4.6	—
45	10.4	151.6	2.4	15.1	9.7	186.5	4.2	9.8
60	8.4	138.1	1.3	31.0	8.5	177.3	3.1	33.6

age for transplanting Basmati seedlings is considered to be 25-35 d.

We assessed the effect of transplanting overage seedlings on yield of Basmati 370 and Basmati 385. Yield

and yield attributes declined significantly with seedling age (see table). The yield decline was partly attributable to fewer productive tillers/hill and fewer spikelets/panicle. □

Relationship of transplanting time and grain yield of Basmati 385

M. Ashraf, S. Mahmood, M. Munsif, and M. Yousaf, Rice Program, National Agricultural Research Centre, P.O. Box 1031, Islamabad, Pakistan

Basmati varieties cover about 85% of the total acreage in Kaalar. Usually transplanting is at the start of the monsoon, within a very short optimum period. But time of transplanting depends on a farmer's resources.

With the release of Basmati 385, we conducted an experiment to determine its optimum transplanting time. The trial was in a randomized complete

Yield and yield-contributing characters of Basmati 385 as affected by transplanting date. Islamabad Pakistan.

Transplanting date	Productive tillers/hill (no.)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield index ^b
15 Jun	11.5 a	194.2 a	4.9 a	93
1 Jul	10.3 a	210.2 a	5.3 a	100
16 Jul	10.5 a	189.6 a	4.4 b	84
31 Jul	9.8 b	178.8 b	3.8 c	72
15 Aug	8.7 b	161.1 c	2.1 d	51

^a Means in a column followed by the same letter are not significant at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b Index taking the yield for 1 Jul plot as 100.

block design with three replications. The crop was kept flooded.

Delayed transplanting significantly reduced grain yield (see table). Highest yield was from plots transplanted 1 Jul, with progressive declines as transplanting was delayed. Yield

decreased 49% from 1 Jul to 15 Aug, at a rate of 58 kg/d per ha. Yield attributes also showed progressive decline with delay in transplanting. The decrease in yield was partly the result of decrease in productive tillers/hill and in spikelets/panicle. □

Variability in rice grain-filling duration

D. Senadhira and Li Guo Fu, Plant Breeding Department, IRRI

Duration of grain filling, defined as the time from flowering to maturity, ranges from about 30 d in the tropics to about 65 d in temperate zones. The variation is considered to be due to temperature difference, not to a varietal character. Modern indica varieties developed for the tropics produce extremely high

yields under temperate conditions. A primary reason for increased yield is a 2-3 wk extension of grain-filling duration.

We examined Bg 90-2 and Bg 380 with longer ripening duration and 19 other varieties with varied agronomic characters for grain-filling duration in dry season 1987 at IRRI. Seeds were sown on wetbed and 4-wk-old seedlings transplanted at 1 plant/hill in 7.2- × 0.9-m plots with 30- × 20-cm row spacing. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Fertilizer was applied basal at 60-40-40 kg NPK/ha. Plots were fully protected against weeds, pests, and diseases.

Panicles were tagged at flowering, when about 5% of spikelets had dehisced anthers. Ten tagged panicles taken at random from each test plot every 4 d from 0 to 46 d after tagging were oven-dried at 48°C for 3 d. Filled and unfilled grains were removed by hand, counted, and weighed.

Increase in grain weight was calculated, adopting Richard's function.